

Kinetics of Acid—Base Catalysed Iodination of Cyclic Ketones—II

N. SATYANARAYANA and E. V. SUNDARAM

Department of Chemistry, University College, Kakatiya University, Warangal-506 009 (A.P.)

Manuscript received 18 May 1979, revised 10 October 1979, accepted 25 August 1980

The kinetics of iodination of cyclic ketones have been studied in different carboxylate buffers and in HClO_4 acid in 50% MeOH - water (v/v). The reaction was found to be first order in ketone and catalyst and zero order in iodine. The activation parameters like ΔE^\ddagger , ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger were evaluated. The catalytic constants of propionate, acetate, lactate and glycolate buffers were measured at 35° for each ketone. The Bronsted coefficient ' β ' for cyclo-pentanone, cyclo-hexanone, cyclo-heptanone and cyclo-octanone were calculated. The anomalous behaviour of high reactivity of cyclo-pentanone was explained on the basis of I-strain concept. The reactions were also studied in various HClO_4 acid concentrations keeping ionic strength constant at 40°. A probable mechanism has been suggested.

THE kinetic studies on the halogenation of aliphatic and aromatic ketones have been reported by a number of workers¹⁻⁵ under different conditions. Not much work seems to have been done on the halogenation of cyclic ketones using general base catalyst except the work done by Bell⁶ and Jagdale⁷.

In continuation of our earlier work on the halogenation of acetophenones⁸, we are communicating in this paper the work on iodination of cyclo-pentanone, cyclo-hexanone, cyclo-heptanone and cyclo-octanone in 50% MeOH - water (v/v) with different carboxylate anions as catalysts.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Cyclo-pentanone (b. p. 130°), cyclo-heptanone (b. p. 179°) were of E. Merck quality and cyclo-hexanone (b. p. 155°) of BDH AnalaR quality was distilled before use. Cyclo-octanone (b. p. 195°) of Koch-light product was used without further purification.

The reaction rates were measured in buffer solutions prepared from NaOH (free from carbonate) and various carboxylic acid solutions in 50% MeOH - water. The concentrations of ketone and iodine were $5 \times 10^{-2}M$ and $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ respectively, with

varying buffer concentrations at a fixed buffer ratio ($r=1$) in the reaction mixture at a constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.8M$) maintained by adding NaClO_4 . The reactions were studied at different temperatures (30 to 50°) with acetate buffer and at 35° with other buffers. A series of reactions were studied with varying acid concentrations keeping ionic strength constant using NaClO_4 and the results were interpreted to explain acid and ionic strength effects. The procedure adopted for the measurement of rate constant and calculations were same as in our earlier publication⁸.

Results and Discussion

The rates of reactions were found to be first order in ketone, and in catalyst and zero order in iodine. The pseudo first order rate constants at different temperatures in 50% MeOH - water (v/v) and the thermodynamic parameters calculated at 35° are given in Table I. The thermodynamic parameters indicate the bimolecular nature of reaction and the stabilisation of transition state compared to that in the reactants.

Bronsted Relationship :

The catalytic constants of different buffers were calculated for the 5, 6, 7 and 8 membered cyclic

TABLE I—RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE IODINATION OF CYCLIC KETONES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES CATALYSED BY ACETATE BUFFER, ACTIVATION PARAMETERS AND BRONSTED COEFFICIENTS AT 35° IN 50% MeOH - WATER (v/v)

[Cyclic ketone]=0.05M, [Acetate]=0.5M, $[I_2]=5 \times 10^{-3}M$, $\mu=0.8$

Cyclic ketones	Rate constant $k \times 10^6 \text{ sec}^{-1}$					ΔH^\ddagger K. cal/mole	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u.	' β '
	Temp. 30°C	35°C	40°C	45°C	50°C			
Cyclo-pentanone	35.48	61.17	111.50	202.00	326.20	21.82	7.0	0.93
Cyclo-hexanone	11.28	18.95	33.35	51.82	88.75	19.53	16.8	0.09
Cyclo-heptanone	3.71	5.92	9.45	13.94	22.40	16.65	23.9	0.16
Cyclo-octanone	5.40	10.50	21.35	34.30	70.06	23.83	4.0	0.22

ketones, by plotting observed rate constant versus buffer salt concentration at a given pH in 50% MeOH—water at 35° and are given in Table 2. The

the slope (k_{H^+}) increases with increase in ionic strength the acid catalysed halogenation is subjected to positive salt effect (Table 4).

TABLE 2—CATALYTIC CONSTANTS OF DIFFERENT BUFFERS AT 35°C IN 50% MeOH—WATER (v/v)

[Ketone] = $5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[I_2] = 5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $\mu = 0.8 M$, Temp. = 35°C

Buffer	pK_a	Catalytic constant $k_b \times 10^4 \text{ l. m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$			
		Cyclo-pentanone	Cyclo-hexanone	Cyclo-heptanone	Cyclo-octanone
Propionate	5.65	147.50	48.50	14.20	29.50
Acetate	5.97	120.00	45.00	115.5	25.00
Lactate	4.57	55.00	36.50	8.40	15.00
Glycolate	4.50	49.10	35.80	8.20	14.40

ionisation constants of propionic, acetic, lactic and glycolic acids required for these calculations were also determined in 50% MeOH—water (v/v) at 35° using the pH metric method⁶. The plot of logarithm of catalytic constant versus pK_a of acid gave Bronsted plots, and the corresponding Bronsted slopes ' β ' for cyclo-pentanone, cyclo-hexanone, cyclo-heptanone and cyclo-octanone were calculated to be 0.33, 0.09, 0.16 and 0.22 respectively. The Bronsted coefficient ' β ' provides a measure of sensitivity of the reaction to the basicity of the acid and also on the stability of the ring^{7, 18}.

Acid and Ionic Strength Effect :

The reactions were studied with varying HClO_4 acid concentrations in 50% MeOH—water (v/v) at 40° and the observed rate constants are computed in Table 3. The ionic strength was maintained

TABLE 3—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON $[H^+]$ AND IONIC STRENGTHS IN 50% MeOH—WATER (v/v)

[Ketone] = 0.01M, $[I_2] = 0.005 M$, Temp. = 40°C

Ionic strength (μ)	$[\text{HClO}_4] M$	Rate constant $k \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$			
		Cyclo-pentanone	Cyclo-hexanone	Cyclo-heptanone	Cyclo-octanone
0.1M	0.025	2.21	7.37	1.47	7.10
	0.050	4.51	14.86	2.86	14.43
	0.075	7.00	21.57	4.43	21.22
	0.100	8.98	30.40	6.09	30.93
	0.050	—	—	2.92	15.89
0.4M	0.100	11.40	36.54	6.41	32.33
	0.150	—	—	9.30	46.25
	0.200	21.80	65.70	13.08	62.18
	0.300	29.55	94.88	—	—
	0.400	36.68	120.20	—	—
0.8M	0.100	12.05	33.78	7.12	32.24
	0.150	18.11	52.52	10.93	49.17
	0.200	22.42	66.79	15.06	63.00
	0.250	29.70	75.51	18.32	80.74

constant for a series of reactions using NaClO_4 salt. A plot of k_{obs} against H^+ ion concentration gave linear curves, which prove that enolisation occurs via conjugate acid species and the intercepts indicate that the reaction occurs via neutral species⁹. Since

TABLE 4—CATALYTIC CONSTANTS OF H^+ IONS AT DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTHS IN 50% MeOH—WATER (v/v)

[Ketone] = 0.01M, $[I_2] = 5 \times 10^{-3} M$, Temp. = 40°C

Ionic strength	Catalytic constant $k_{H^+} \times 10^4 \text{ l. m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$			
	Cyclo-pentanone	Cyclo-hexanone	Cyclo-heptanone	Cyclo-octanone
$\mu = 0.1 M$	9.53	27.80	5.97	28.57
$\mu = 0.4 M$	10.17	28.80	6.53	30.67
$\mu = 0.8 M$	11.57	33.30	7.45	32.30

Mechanism :

The reactivity of cyclo-pentanone in base catalyst is 3 to 4 times greater than cyclo-hexanone, which is confirmed both from the observed rate constants as well as from Bronsted slopes. According to classical theory cyclo-hexanone can be formed without appreciable strain, while cyclo-pentanone with considerable strain. On this basis cyclo-hexanone should be a stronger acid and more reactive towards halogenation than cyclo-pentanone. But the observation is in opposite direction to that anticipated. Similar anomaly has been observed in case of halogenation of 2-carbomethoxy esters⁶, but no explanation was given. This may be explained on the basis of I-strain concept. In the enolate ion the hybridisation of α -carbon atom changes from SP^3 to SP^2 , four bond oppositions are relieved, hence its strain is decreased. This favours SP^3 to SP^2 transition and corresponding displacement reactions in cyclo-pentanone systems are relatively rapid. In the six membered ring, however, the rigid (chain) form is free of bond oppositions. Change of hybridisation from SP^3 to SP^2 produces bond oppositions and is therefore resisted. Correspondingly displacement reactions in cyclo-hexyl systems are relatively slow. Similar considerations apply to seven membered rings which are also mobile and beset with bond oppositions of adjacent C—H bonds, although to a somewhat lesser extent than the five membered rings.

The medium-sized rings like cyclo-octanone is beset with angle deformations, bond opposition, and trans annular interactions. Most of these are due to hydrogen-hydrogen interreactions, the SP^2 configuration, with its lesser number of C—H bonds is therefore favoured¹⁰ over SP^3 . This was confirmed in case of acetolysis of cyclo-alkyl tosylates¹¹, reaction of cyclo-alkyl bromides with lithium or potassium iodide¹², and solvolysis of methyl cyclo-alkyl chlorides in 80% ethanol^{13, 14}. The observed rate constants in buffers show that the sequence of halogenation is cyclo-pentanone > cyclo-hexanone > cyclo-octanone > cyclo-heptanone. However, our results indicate some irregularity in case of cyclo-heptanone which is slower than expected. This

indicates that effects other than I-strain may be important, particularly polar factors may also have to be considered. Similar anomalies were observed by Roberts and co-workers^{1,5}.

The reactivity order in acid catalysis is cyclohexanone ~ cyclo-octanone > cyclo-pentanone > cyclo-heptanone. The sequence is reverse of that observed for base catalysis and is in confirmity with the results of Murthy^{1,6}. Cyclo-heptanone is less reactive even in acid catalyst.

References

1. A. LAPWORTH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, **85**, 30.
2. E. D. HUGHES, WATSON and YATES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 3318.
3. R. P. BELL and P. M. LID WELL, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1940, **A176**, 88.
4. L. N. PATNAIK, P. L. NAIK and M. K. ROUT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 668.
5. D. N. NANDA, P. L. NAIK and M. K. ROUT, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 469.
6. R. P. BELL and H. C. GOLD SMITH, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1952, **A210**, 322.
7. M. H. JAGDALE and B. S. MANE, *Sci. J. Shivaji Univ.*, 1975, **15**, 131.
8. N. SATYANARAYANA and E. V. SUNDARAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 886.
9. M. M. MHALA and K. J. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 1092.
10. V. PRELOG, 'Some Newer Developments of the Chemistry of the Medium sized Ring Compounds', *Bull. Soc. Chim., France*, 1960, 1433.
11. H. C. BROWN and G. HAM, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 2735.
12. P. J. C. FIERMS and P. VERSCHULDEN, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belges*, 1952, **61**, 427, 609.
13. H. C. BROWN, R. S. FLETCHER and R. B. JOHANNESON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 212.
14. H. C. BROWN and M. BORKOWSKI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 1894.
15. J. D. ROBERTS and V. C. CHAMBERS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5034.
16. P. S. RADHAKRISHNA MURTHY and D. K. MAHAPATRO, 'Annual Convention of Chemists,' 1978 (Waltair) p. 80 (Org).
17. O. ROGNE, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1971, 1855.
18. O. ROGNE, *J. Chem. Soc. Perkin II*, 1972, 489.